

EXPLORATION OF THE NOVEL CONCEPT OF RESTORATIVE AGILE BIOREFINING

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ABSTRACT: This paper concerns the exploration of the concept of agile and restorative biorefining through a cross-disciplinary research study. We promote a small-scale, highly flexible production biorefining system that strives in an uncertain environment to respond to supply/demand and market changes. The agile paradigm allows interconnecting localised biorefineries for better source and production integration. A formal definition for the concept is introduced.

Keywords: biobased economy, biochemical, small-scale application, strategy, sustainability, supply chain.

1 INTRODUCTION

Bioresources are essential to modern living and consumers need to be able to trust that the system has developed to ensure continuous supply. Through improving the use of waste as building blocks of these bioresources we will reduce the individual footprints on the environment, whilst enhancing consumer lifestyles through novel or reformulated products. An enterprise that adopts a restorative approach will proactively move the boundary of what it is taking into account and begins to take responsibility not only for its internal systems but also for the larger social and natural systems [1]. The global market for biorefineries is £350Bn rising to £550Bn by 2021 [2]. The current approach to biorefining is a large-scale plant under a single large-scale investment [3]. The UK's leading biorefinery (Wissington) typically produces 400k tonnes of sugar every year. Co-products include about 350k tonnes of sugar beet pulp (SBP), 15k tonnes of vinasse, and up to 64k tonnes of bioethanol every year. The Wissington biorefinery is a world-class example of a fixed location, fixed infrastructure, single and high-volume feedstock biorefinery [3]. In this exploratory study, we investigate an alternative approach to biorefining, which could unlock a new opportunity for circular economy at scale.

Transforming or extracting value from biomass is often expensive, especially without connecting to the business models required to make it economically viable [4]. The marketplace lacks innovation for the utilisation of this value, linked to a lack of transparency for the available value streams. To address this we need technological, economic, and social innovation on the concept of agile biorefining to break down these barriers, delivering change across the system.

Rather than a single, large-scale plant dedicated to a specific waste stream, we now imagine a set of independent manufacturing biorefinery plants that can collaborate and compete to maximise the total value (economic, environmental and social) of a waste stream. In this study, we explore a new biorefining approach: Agile biorefineries that are both feedstock flexible, infrastructure flexible and with a physical size that enables several low-cost localised biorefineries to be feasible, hence spreading the benefits across locations.

The main research methods used here start with a cross-disciplinary literature review across industrial symbiosis, agile manufacturing and supply chain management, flexible and re-distributed manufacturing, and biorefinery and bioeconomy, followed by consultations with industry experts in biorefining. The

following research questions are answered:

- What are the key characteristics of an agile and restorative biorefinery?
- Which feedstocks would be viable in an agile restorative biorefinery?
- How does agility enable Circular Economy and sustainability?

A first observation of agile in biorefinery was found in [5], which consisted in developing a metamodel that relies on the integration of digital concepts to reach agile biorefining systems. In the current work, we seek to explore, expand, and further integrate a vision of characteristics of the restorative and agile biorefinery concept and propose a formal definition for it.

2 CHARACTERISTICS OF AN AGILE AND RESTORATIVE BIOREFINERY

Agile manufacturing can be defined as "... the capability of surviving and prospering in a competitive environment of continuous and unpredictable change by reacting quickly and effectively to changing markets, driven by customer-designed products and service" [6,7]. Some key concepts related to agility are flexibility in manufacturing, easy access to integrated data, and modular production facilities [6]. Supply chain agility is defined as a strategic ability that assists organizations rapidly in sense and responding to internal and external uncertainties via effective integration of supply chain relationships [8]. It allows responding to changes, which can originate in the type of product and the quantity being produced, market dynamics, sourcing and procurement, among others, in a timely and effective manner [9]. Information systems play a vital role to integrate and coordinate data and information between supplier and market relationships. We shall discuss the role of these characteristics in the context of biorefinery systems.

Concept Proposition:

An agile restorative biorefinery involves a relatively low capital investment modular (adaptable) facility, deployed locally (uses local, short-distance available resources), capable of utilising different feedstocks (flexible), including wastes, in a small-scale but high yield production, which works in tandem and focusing in generating value across all stakeholders.

Figure 1 - Restorative agile biorefinery concept characteristics.

2.1 Flexible and Reconfigurable

From a manufacturing standpoint, flexibility attains the capacity of how fast the company converts its process(es) from making an old line of products to producing a new product. Early definitions are based on the notion of adaptability to uncertainties [10], which still retains much of the essence given to flexible manufacturing systems. The ability to change a production schedule, modify a part, or handle multiple parts. The ability to rapidly increase or decrease production levels of shift capacity from one product to another. The reconfigurable manufacturing paradigm was introduced as a necessity to cope with relatively large fluctuations in product demand and mix caused by market disturbances [11].

To successfully construct the concept of agile biorefinery, one must take these factors into account and consider their integration into the design, planning and operational management of biorefineries. Biorefineries need to be designed for flexibility so that they can adapt easily to changes in feedstock supply and/or demand for value-added products [12].

2.2 Small-scale, modularity and decentralization

Larger centralized processing plants benefit from economies of scale due to reduced marginal costs, better processing yields, and returns on investment. For these reasons, small-scale processes greatly defy economies of scale. However, [13] argue that economies of scale may not be as important in the biomass-based sector as it is in fossil-based sectors due to the sparsity of biomass energy density and reduced cost of technology.

Some of the advantages of small-scale processes are outlined in terms of reduced transportation costs using local resources, farmer benefits, storage, and logistical ease, and better capabilities in re-using waste and heat [13]. These are expected to have lower initial investments and operational costs, lower energy requirements, and less capital-intensive technology [14].

Small-scale biorefineries are typically deployed locally (near feedstock sources) and in rural areas. This contributes to the decentralization of the processing chain and possibly establishes deeper collaboration bonds with farmers and suppliers of biomass. It is this alignment and close cooperation that enables the agility capabilities of the system (company, supply chain).

The single large-scale facility can be split into several smaller ones by leveraging local sources of feedstock and creating an interconnected network of biorefineries. Using distributed manufacturing to promote decentralization by addressing location and scale in terms of technology, processes, systems, and business strategies [15]. Collaborative approaches may facilitate production escalation by downstream integration and processing of flows [16].

The modularity comes into play as several production units can be added to up-scale the production process as needed, and removed, to de-scale the process. Designing a modularity system may favour agility by implementing several singular low-cost but highly effective modules [17]. These modules can be (re)deployed depending on the locally available biomass and contain new conversion processes adapted to the product being produced. This is linked with the micro-factory concept which integrates automatised production of customised products, delivered on-demand, in which capacity is increased by embedding in a network with other micro-factories [18].

2.3 Feedstocks and technology selection for agile

A biorefinery is typically defined by the type of feedstock and conversion process applied [19]. The first-generation feedstocks are already very compromised due to global food supply shortages and have been reported to increase the prices of food and animal feed [20]. This tendency is being aggravated by the climate crisis and increased human population, thus not allowing concomitant use for sustainable biorefining.

Therefore, efforts should be directed towards non-food competing feedstocks, which means using biowastes and by-products from several agro-food and non-agro-food sectors in cross-sectorial exchanges. These streams include lignocellulosic materials, green fertilizers, and other farm residues (e.g., corn stover), kitchen waste, agro-food waste, industrial waste, and forestry wastes [21]. A waste biorefinery is said of capable producing fuels, power, heat, and value-added products [22]. For example, the use of lignocellulosic materials allows different platforms to be deployed for extraction of intermediate products such as lignin, hemicellulose, which could be further processed for value-added products such as bacterial cellulose, biopolymers, and biosolvents [23]. Consequently, these have several uses by different industrial sectors such as the medical, pharmaceutical, textile, chemical, among others.

To take advantage of the relatively low processing capacity (due to scale), the production system needs to be highly efficient in terms of value-added. The production processes and thus, technology selection needs to be carefully selected, to allow the production of high-margin products at minimal resource use. There are reports of reduced capital costs in these integrative multi-productive systems [24], and of effectiveness in maximising biomass yield and efficiency [25]. Not all technologies are appropriate for agile biorefining, and consequently, a key design requirement is to effectively optimize chosen supply (raw material) and the portfolio of products to be produced. The biochemical pathway seems promising from a small-scale and low-cost standpoint [26]. Several studies also consider the use of biomass fractionation technologies to optimize efficiency [27,28].

2.4 Role of IoT and Information Technologies

Information technologies are at the core of an agile

system as it allows the integration of processes, technology, people, and organizations [6]. It entails the creation of virtual-based systems, essential for deepening supply-buyer collaborations, and forecasting and satisfying market demands. An agile biorefinery urges to be in constant awareness of the state of the supply given its scale and localized production. Data analytics and the use of I4.0 to sustain and validate operations are likely to have a significant role in streamlining the biorefinery supply chain and operations and optimising purchasing and production activities. The HereWear H2020 project [29] works exactly in integrating digitalised production at a local scale for on-demand textile production and clothing goods. It may have a glimpse of what is required to successfully integrate and transition to agile and restorative biorefining.

3 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The concept of agile and restorative biorefineries is built and the main characteristics are addressed. It pertains to the integration of innovative manufacturing paradigms with the role and characteristics of a biorefinery in the circular economy. An agile biorefinery is a biorefinery that is built to thrive in an uncertain environment, benefitting from small-scale localised production with easy to implement technologies that are feedstock flexible. Working in a small-scale environment requires a closer connection between the sourcing of materials and wastes and the production steps at the biorefinery. A network of localized biorefineries is formed through information systems and integrated with downstream industries for the concomitant production of value-added products and biofuels at a global scale.

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